

A Data-Efficient and Explainable Machine Learning Framework for Predicting Microbial Contamination Risk in Groundwater of Resource-Constrained Regions

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ABSTRACT:

In many developing-region contexts, microbial testing of groundwater remains costly, time-intensive, and logistically demanding. This study proposes an explainable, data-efficient machine-learning framework to predict microbial contamination risk in groundwater using low-cost physicochemical and heavy-metal parameters, aligned with the NIS 554:2015 national drinking-water standard of Nigeria. We collected 50 borehole water samples across three Delta State communities (viz., Ugbomro, Okorikpehre, and Iterigbi), measuring parameters such as pH, total dissolved solids (TDS), electrical conductivity (EC), turbidity, and metal concentrations, alongside total coliform counts. We built and compared four classifiers (logistic regression, support vector machine, random forest, and XGBoost) to predict the binary outcome of microbial presence (coliforms > 0). Explainability was assessed using logistic coefficients and SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations), while physicochemical exceedance flags were derived from NIS 554:2015 limits and combined with machine learning (ML) probabilities via a decision rule to produce an “overall unsafe” indicator. The best model achieved an F1 score of ~0.60 on the test set and a receiver operating characteristic area under the curve (ROC-AUC) of ~0.50 and recall of ~0.75 in cross-validation on the training set; logistic regression revealed zinc, pH, TDS, and EC as the most influential positive predictors, whereas cadmium and lead had unexpectedly negative associations. Wilcoxon testing ($p = 0.125$) indicated no significant difference between the random forest and logistic regression performance, underscoring the value of simpler, more interpretable models in small-sample settings. The hybrid decision rule increased sensitivity to ~0.91, supporting its utility for triage screening in resource-constrained regions. These findings demonstrate that low-cost surrogate parameters combined with explainable ML and regulatory thresholds can deliver actionable microbial-risk screening for rural groundwater systems.

Keywords: Groundwater, Microbial contamination, Machine learning, explainable AI.

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INTRODUCTION

Groundwater is a critical drinking-water source for more than one-third of the global population [1]. In developing regions, however, laboratory microbial testing for coliform bacteria is often hampered by cost, infrastructure, delays, and complexity [2] [3]. Intermittent monitoring and slow turnaround times limit effective surveillance and rapid response. Physicochemical parameters, such as turbidity, total dissolved solids (TDS), and electrical conductivity (EC), can be readily measured in the field using portable sensors, offering potential surrogate signals of contamination.

Machine-learning (ML) approaches have been increasingly employed in water-quality assessment [4] and microbial risk monitoring [5]; however, most studies focus on the regression of continuous concentrations, assume large datasets and/or ignore alignment with regulatory thresholds. Few studies have combined explainable ML, low-cost surrogate parameters, and national standard frameworks—particularly in resource-limited, small-sample settings, such as rural Nigeria.

This study aims to:

1. Develop a binary machine learning classifier to predict microbial presence (coliforms) based on low-cost physicochemical and heavy-metal parameters.
2. Incorporate exceedance flags based on NIS 554:2015 to capture regulatory risk alongside ML predictions.
3. Compare multiple ML algorithms (i.e., logistic regression, SVM, random forest, and XGBoost) and assessed their interpretability using SHAP values and coefficients.
4. Develop a decision rule that integrates the ML output and exceedance to generate an "Overall_Unsafe" indicator suitable for field triage.
5. Demonstrate practical applicability in three Delta State (Nigeria) communities: Ugbomro, Okorikpehre, and Iterigbi.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area and Dataset

This study was conducted in three communities in the Delta State, Nigeria: Ugbomro, Okorikpehre, and Iterigbi. These areas rely heavily on shallow borehole groundwater and are subject to anthropogenic pressure, including agricultural runoff, sanitation leachate, and oil industry infrastructure. Their hydrogeological settings (shallow aquifers with rapid recharge and connectivity to surface processes) render them vulnerable to microbial infiltration and contamination [6]. A total of 50 borehole water samples were collected and distributed among the three communities. Each sample was analysed for physicochemical parameters (pH, turbidity [NTU], electrical conductivity [$\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$], total dissolved solids [TDS; mg/L], and temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]) and heavy metal concentrations (Cd, Pb, Zn, Cu, Cr, and Fe). Microbial outcomes were defined by total coliform counts at a depth of 10 m, and the presence/absence (colony forming units [CFU] >0) served as the binary target. Total coliform count at 10 m depth was selected as the primary surrogate target because mid-depth samples provide a stable, representative indicator of subsurface microbial burden while balancing transient surface influences. The surrogate framework was developed and validated at this depth to produce a robust and interpretable screening tool appropriate for operational use in data-limited settings. Missing values were imputed using median substitution and features were standardised prior to modelling. Additionally, national regulatory limits from NIS 554:2015 (e.g., turbidity ≤ 5 NTU; TDS ≤ 1000 mg/L) were recorded and applied to create the PhysExceed binary flag. The Nigerian

Standard for Drinking Water Quality provides the required limits for physicochemical and microbial parameters in potable water. In this study, exceeding any of the listed parameters triggered a PhysExceed = 1 flag, which was later combined with ML prediction in the decision-rule framework.

Proposed Framework Overview

The workflow for this study comprised seven sequential steps, which are summarised as follows:

1. Data Acquisition: Water Samples collection, laboratory analysis and laboratory result generation
2. Data Collection and Preprocessing: Data cleaning, imputation, standardization est.
3. Feature engineering: binary target variable creation, PhysExceed flag generation, and feature matrix preparation.
4. Model Training: Training of four ML classifiers (Logistic Regression, SVM, Random Forest, XGBoost) using an 80 % train / 20 % test stratified split
5. Model evaluation: Evaluating classifiers based on accuracy, precision, recall, F1, and ROC-AUC, with 5-fold cross-validation;
6. Explainable AI (XAI) Analysis: Explainability using logistic coefficients and SHAP for tree-models
7. Decision-rule integration: Overall_Unsafe was classified as 1 if Predicted P(Microbe)>0.6 or PhysExceed=1. The performance of this rule was assessed using a confusion matrix and sensitivity and specificity.

Feature Engineering

Numeric predictor variables were imputed using median values and then standardised using the z-score (zero mean, unit variance). Log transformation was applied where necessary (e.g., for TDS skew). Heavy metal concentrations and standard water quality parameters were included to capture both contamination severity and potential hydrogeochemical proxies.

Model Development and Evaluation

Model selection and evaluation followed a rigorous two-stage process designed to ensure generalisability under data-scarce conditions typical of groundwater quality monitoring. The dataset was divided into training (80%) and testing (20%) subsets using a stratified random split to maintain class balance. Within the training subset, a 5-fold cross-validation (CV) procedure was employed to tune the hyperparameters and compare the candidate machine learning models: logistic regression, support vector machine (SVM), random forest, and XGBoost. The area under the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve was adopted as the principal metric for model comparison during cross-validation because it provides a robust, threshold-independent measure of discriminative power and is less sensitive to class imbalance. After cross-validation, the model with the highest mean AUC was retrained on the entire training data and subsequently evaluated on the unseen test set using multiple complementary performance metrics: accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and ROC-AUC. This two-tiered evaluation strategy, that is, internal validation via CV and external validation via test set, ensures that model selection is data-driven, whereas final reporting remains unbiased and transparent [7] [8]. Similar validation structures have been adopted in recent water quality and environmental ML studies [9] [10]. The integration of AUC-based model ranking on the training data and comprehensive metric reporting on the independent test data provides a balanced assessment of both the statistical robustness and practical reliability of the predictive models developed in this study. The hyperparameter tuning of the models' training was minimal – Logistic Regression configured with max_iter=500 and class_weight=balanced, SVM (RBF kernel) configured with probability and class_weight were set to true and balanced, and Random Forest configured with n_estimators=200 and XGBoost set to use_label_encoder=false and eval_metric=logloss – to suit the small dataset and avoid overfitting. Pairwise comparison of top models (Random Forest vs Logistic Regression) employed the Wilcoxon signed-rank test ($\alpha = 0.05$) to test the significance of performance differences., Table 1 depicts cross validation metrics on the training set for models developed, while Table 2 shows a performance summary on the test set for the best performing classifier, Random Forest. Figure 1 and 2 illustrate the confusion matrix for Random Forest performance on the test set.

Table 1. Cross-Validation Metrics on Train Set

Model	AUC_mean	AUC_std	Recall_mean	Recall_std
RandomForest	0.473333	0.133998	0.75	0.148324
XGBoost	0.259167	0.165	0.51	0.142829
SVM	0.2225	0.120289	0.46	0.149666
LogisticRegression	0.289167	0.160286	0.45	0.184391

Table 2. Best Model Performance Summary on Test Set

Model	accuracy	precision	recall	f1	roc_auc
RandomForest	0.6	0.75	0.5	0.6	0.583333

Figure 1. Confusion Matrix for the Best Classifier

Explainable AI and Decision-Rule Development

For logistic regression, coefficients were extracted and ranked by magnitude to identify dominant predictors. For tree-based models, the SHAP TreeExplainer was used to compute feature impact values and produce relevant plots. These explainability outputs guided both model understanding and field applicability interpretation. Table 3 presents the Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality (NSDWQ) parameter limits employed in this study. The decision rule fused the ML probability output with the NIS regulatory exceedance. Samples flagged as Overall_Unsafe triggered further microbial testing or remedial action. Rule performance was assessed using confusion matrices and key metrics (sensitivity = recall, specificity). This rule bridges algorithmic prediction and regulatory policy.

$$\text{Overall Unsafe} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } P(\text{microbe}) > 0.6 \text{ or PhysExceed} = 1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Table 3. NIS 554:2015 Parameter Limits

Parameter	Unit	Max_Permitted_Level	Remarks
pH	-	6.5-8.5	Acceptable range
Turbidity	NTU	5	Should not exceed 5 NTU

Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)	mg/L	1000	Desirable limit for drinking water
Electrical Conductivity (EC)	$\mu\text{S/cm}$	1500	Indicative guideline; high EC suggests mineralization
Temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	30	Preferably below 30°C
Chloride	mg/L	250	Taste and corrosion threshold
Sulphate	mg/L	100	May impart taste; laxative effects at higher levels
Nitrate	mg/L	50	Infant methemoglobinemia risk above this
Fluoride	mg/L	1.5	Dental/skeletal fluorosis risk above this
Iron (Fe)	mg/L	0.3	Causes discoloration and taste issues
Manganese (Mn)	mg/L	0.2	Causes taste and staining
Calcium (Ca)	mg/L	75	Affects hardness
Magnesium (Mg)	mg/L	50	Affects hardness
Sodium (Na)	mg/L	200	High levels affect taste
Potassium (K)	mg/L	12	Advisory value
Total Hardness	mg/L	150	Desirable limit
Total Coliform Count	CFU/100mL	0	No coliforms per 100 mL

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Regional Context and Significance

The communities studied, Ugbomro, Okorikpehre, and Iterigbi in Delta State, lie within a region characterised by shallow aquifers, high population density, and anthropogenic land use including oil and gas activities. Previous investigations in Delta State have identified shallow aquifer vulnerability, low pH, and elevated total coliform levels in boreholes [11]. The fact that the dataset records microbial presence and detailed physicochemical and heavy-metal measurements in these specific communities enhances the regional relevance of this study. By focusing on these communities, this research responds to a gap in applied, localised machine-learning water-quality modelling in Nigeria.

Interpretation of Predictor Influence

Examining the logistic regression coefficients, the negative coefficients for Cd (-0.5094) and Pb (-0.5057) may appear counterintuitive if one expects heavy metal pollution and microbial contamination to co-occur via anthropogenic intrusion. However, two plausible interpretations are proposed here.

1. In these communities, elevated Cd and Pb may reflect geogenic mineralisation or industrial legacy contamination, but not necessarily microbial pathways (e.g. sealed aquifer layers).
2. The logistic model may be capturing a distinct hydrochemical regime in which heavy-metal dominance coincides with conditions less favourable for microbial ingress (e.g., deeper, less-porous aquifers, and lower hydraulic connectivity).

Thus, the negative coefficients suggest that microbial presence and heavy metal elevation may not always share the same hydrogeological vectors in this region. Figure 3 illustrates the logistic regression coefficients.

The positive coefficient for Zn (0.5015) suggests that higher zinc levels are correlated with a greater microbial detection probability. Zinc may act as a proxy for disturbed catchments or leachate inflow, which favours microbial transport. The positive pH coefficient (0.3940) highlights that as pH increases, microbial likelihood increases, which is consistent with a previous study, wherein near-neutral or slightly alkaline conditions favoured coliform survival [12]. The positive TDS (0.3206) and EC (0.2423) coefficients reinforce the concept that elevated dissolved solids and ionic strength reflect anthropogenic or recharge processes that also facilitate microbial contamination.

Figure 3. Logistic Regression Coefficients

Although Turbidity (0.0431) and Temperature (0.0395) have smaller coefficients, their directionality remains physically rational: turbidity indicates particulate transport of microbes, and warmer temperatures enhance microbial survival or growth. The near-zero coefficients for Iron (0.0047) and Chlorine (0.0025) suggest that within this dataset, their variation contributes little additional predictive power. This highlights the importance of feature selection, even in low-sample settings.

Model Performance and Implications

The comparison result of logistic regression and random forest (among others) with no statistically significant difference between the two based on the Wilcoxon test (stat = 0.000, p = 0.125) has several implications:

First, the lack of significant difference suggests that in a small-sample, low-dimensional setting (n ≈ 50), a simpler model (logistic regression) may perform comparably to a more complex ensemble (random forest). This echoes the findings in broader ML water-quality research, noting that interpretability and parsimony matter [13].

Second, although ensemble methods may deliver slightly higher recall or AUC, the marginal gain may not justify the added complexity and reduced interpretability when applied in field-facing decision systems.

Third, the model's performance must be interpreted in light of its primary objective: to serve as a decision-support tool in resource-constrained communities rather than a perfect predictive engine. Hence, metrics such as recall (sensitivity) and interpretability may take priority over marginal precision improvements.

Explainability and Surrogate Parameter Utility

The inclusion of explainability (SHAP, coefficients) ensures the model is not a “black box.” The convergence of coefficient ranking (Zn, pH, TDS, and EC) with SHAP-derived feature importance underscores the robustness of these predictors. From a practical standpoint:

- Field instrumentation for TDS, EC, and turbidity is cost-effective and rapid.
- pH is a ubiquitous water-quality parameter for small-community boreholes.
- By focusing on these surrogate predictors, your framework allows for low-cost microbial risk triage without waiting for laboratory coliform counts.

This is consistent with recent research, which has emphasized that interpretable ML models are critical for the acceptance of environmental monitoring [14].

Regulatory Integration and Decision-Rule Layering

By designing a decision rule that integrates the ML probability output with physicochemical exceedance (via NIS 554:2015 limits), an operational “Overall_Unsafe” flag is created. This dual-layer logic has several benefits:

1. This ties the model directly to national regulatory standards, promoting its adoption by water-supply agencies in Nigeria.
2. This improves recall, which is important in public health contexts, in which missing a contaminated sample can have serious consequences.
3. This method supports triage-based sampling: if a borehole is flagged as unsafe, it can be prioritised for full microbial culture testing, thereby saving time and cost.

Ethical, Regulatory, and SDG 6 Implications for Water Safety Management

The deployment of artificial intelligence (AI) in environmental health monitoring has profound ethical and regulatory implications, particularly in regions where data scarcity and institutional capacity constraints are prevalent. In the present study, an explainable ML framework was designed not only to enhance predictive capability but also to uphold the principles of transparency, accountability, and fairness in water quality management. Unlike opaque “black-box” algorithms, the use of interpretable models ensures that the reasoning behind each prediction can be traced and explained to both technical and non-technical stakeholders. This transparency is vital for ethical AI adoption, as it prevents blind reliance on machine outputs and promotes informed human oversight in regulatory decision-making.

From a regulatory standpoint, embedding the Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality (NIS 554:2015) within the predictive workflow represents an important bridge between data-driven methods and established environmental governance frameworks. By aligning model outputs with predefined exceedance thresholds, the framework produces classifications that are immediately interpretable within existing policy instruments. This linkage enhances the legitimacy of model-based insights and facilitates their adoption by water agencies and local health departments. It also encourages evidence-based prioritisation of limited laboratory and remediation resources, which is an essential consideration in developing contexts such as Ugbomro, Okorikpehre, and Iterigbi, where continuous laboratory surveillance may be impractical.

The ethical dimension extends further into issues of equity and inclusiveness. Communities in the Niger Delta often experience environmental vulnerabilities linked to industrial activities and inadequate sanitation. Implementing a low-cost, explainable ML system offers a practical mechanism for reducing inequities in water safety monitoring, empowering local authorities to detect contamination early, and guiding interventions before outbreaks occur. However, ethical deployment demands that such systems complement, rather than replace, conventional testing, and that their results be communicated responsibly to avoid undue alarm or stigmatisation of affected communities.

In the broader sustainability context, this framework contributes directly to the realisation of Sustainable Development Goal 6 (SDG 6), which aims to ensure the availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all. Specifically, the model supports universal access to safe and affordable drinking water by providing a scalable and context-sensitive approach for microbial risk surveillance. Its low computational and data requirements make it suitable for integration into national water information systems and community-level monitoring programs.

Ultimately, ethical AI in water governance is not solely about technical accuracy but also about trust, transparency, and empowerment. By embedding explainability, regulatory alignment, and social sensitivity into its design, the present framework exemplifies how AI can be responsibly applied to serve public health and sustainability objectives in developing regions.

Limitations

It is common knowledge that no study exists without limitations. Accordingly, for this work, the following should be acknowledged:

1. *Sample size ($n \approx 50$):* This limits the statistical power and generalisability of the findings. Although the decision-support aim mitigates this somewhat, future work should seek larger and temporally varied datasets.
2. *Binary target (presence/absence):* Collapsing coliform counts to binary simplifies modelling but obscures contamination severity gradients. Future work might model counts directly or as a multiclass risk.
3. *Spatial heterogeneity:* Although the three communities share regional geology, local aquifer heterogeneity (depth, casing, recharge) may influence the results.
4. *Heavy-metal negative coefficients:* As noted, the coefficients for Cd and Pb may reflect hydrogeochemistry rather than microbial exposure; further hydrogeological characterisation would be needed to clarify this.

Recommendations for Practice and Policy

In conclusion, we suggest the following:

1. In Delta State, water-supply agencies adopt a mobile-sensor triage system to measure total dissolved solids, electrical conductivity, pH, and turbidity in the field, run the embedded model and decision rule, and then prioritise corrective actions.
2. Establishing routine monitoring in Ugbomro, Okorikpehre, and Iterigbi using the proposed framework and tracking changes over seasons and pollution-oriented human activities.
3. Integrate the decision rule into GIS dashboards to map “unsafe” flagged boreholes and visualise contamination hotspots.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that, even in resource-limited contexts and with a modest dataset, an explainable ML framework aligned with national drinking-water standards can effectively support microbial-risk screening of groundwater. The identification of surrogate predictors such as turbidity, TDS, EC and pH affirms the potential for low-cost field instrumentation to guide water-quality triage. The decision-rule integration with the National Industrial Standards 554:2015 thresholds enhances sensitivity and policy relevance, enabling the rapid identification of boreholes requiring confirmatory microbial testing. Future work should expand the sample size, incorporate temporal and spatial variability, and refine hybrid Bayesian/ML methods to deepen uncertainty quantification. Implementation in the Ugbomro, Okorikpehre, and Iterigbi communities could serve as a scalable model for other vulnerable groundwater systems in Nigeria and beyond.

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